

Draft reporting standard in line with the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC):

Reporting the Viability of Secondary Raw Material Recovery Projects and Their Quantities

Deliverable 1.3

Project:	Future Availability of Secondary Raw Materials
Acronym:	FutuRaM
Grant Agreement:	101058522
Funding Scheme:	Horizon Europe
Webpage:	www.futuram.eu
Work Package:	WP 1
Work Package Leader:	Empa
Deliverable Title:	Draft reporting standard in line with the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC)
Deliverable Leader:	Empa
Version:	V1
Status:	Final
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Due Date:	28.02.2026
Date Of Submission:	11.03.2026
Dissemination Level:	Public

Version History

VER. NO.	DATE	REASONS FOR RELEASE	RESPONSIBLE
VO.1	25.11.2025	Feedback collection on structure and content from project partners involved in D1.3 development	Empa
VO.2	14.01.2026	Review of the first draft without Chapter 4.3 by project partners involved in D1.3 development	Empa
VO.3	13.02.2026	Review of the completed version by project partners involved in D1.3 development	Empa
VO.4	27.02.2026	Final review by FutuRaM PMT members	Empa
V1	11.03.2016	Submission	Empa

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable suggests the structure and content of a reporting standard to report the viability of secondary raw material recovery projects and their quantities in line with the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC). This is a working document drafted for the attention of the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) Expert Group on Resource Management (EGRM) as an initial step toward the development of a reporting standard.

The guidelines and guidance in this document are based on the procedures developed in the FutuRaM project for applying UNFC to projects related to the recovery of secondary raw materials. The document explains what information and data should be provided for reporting the environmental-social-economic viability (E-axis) and technical feasibility of secondary raw materials recovery projects (F-axis). It also describes how to report the estimated quantities of secondary raw materials and their corresponding degree of confidence (G-axis), in accordance with the principles of the UNFC. It provides structured frameworks for reporting this information, along with relevant terminology and explanations, and outlines the minimum requirements for the information to be provided. These frameworks are based on the development phase of a project, covering the screening, pre-feasibility, and feasibility study phases.

Accordingly, it is suggested that the following aspects be reported for a project in the screening phase related to secondary raw material recovery in line with the UNFC:

1. Project profile
2. Degree of confidence in materials quantities at source (G-axis)
3. Evaluation of precondition background information
4. Scope of the project
5. Preliminary technical considerations (F-axis)
6. Preliminary economic assessment (E-axis)
7. Preliminary environmental and social impact assessment (E-axis)
8. Legal considerations (E-axis)
9. Stakeholders' information
10. UNFC categorization and classification

For projects in the pre-feasibility and feasibility study phases, the structure and content of the reported information differ, particularly because more detailed investigations can be carried out through the assessment of controlling factors related to E- and F-axes. Accordingly, the following aspects should be included when reporting such projects in line with the UNFC:

1. Project profile
2. Definition of the project and the context of evaluation
3. Degree of confidence in quantities of outputs (G-axis)
4. Controlling factors evaluation (E- and F-axes)
5. Categorization and classification

At the end, to facilitate the development of a reporting standard, the Chapter "Outlook" presents the proposed next steps and roadmap for establishing a reporting standard. It identifies areas requiring further technical refinement and development to support reporting and outlines the stakeholder consultation and institutional endorsement processes necessary for its formal recognition. As this

deliverable was drafted for the attention of the UNECE EGRM as an initial step toward the development of a reporting standard, it is assumed that the UNECE EGRM will continue this work and lead the further development of the reporting standard. The proposed reporting standard is expected to support the reporting of information on secondary raw material recovery projects by project developers and other reporting entities to a wide range of end users, including investors and their professional advisers, authorities, the public, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs).

2 Introduction

Various guidance and specifications have been developed by the UNECE on the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) to explain how to apply it in classifying projects related to primary and secondary raw materials, including "UNFC 2019" (UNECE, 2020b), "UNFC Guidance Europe: Guidance for the Application of UNFC for Minerals and Anthropogenic Resources" (UNECE, 2022b), and "Supplementary Specifications for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources to Anthropogenic Resources" (UNECE, 2025). However, there is no guidance nor a reporting standard on how to report on classification of a project in accordance with UNFC. Such a reporting standard is crucial to harmonize reporting and facilitate transparent communication of a project with its various stakeholders for better decision-making.

Secondary raw material (anthropogenic resource) recovery may occur at different stages of a resource value chain and involve a variety of stakeholders who need and expect different data and information. A report is one of the main tools for communicating project information to the different parties; hence, it is crucial to include all the necessary information clearly and in an easy-to-follow format. The UNFC describes a secondary raw material recovery project in terms of its environmental, social, economic, legal, and technical feasibility, as well as the degree of confidence in the estimated quantity of materials to be recovered. Starting from an initial idea, a project evolves step by step until it reaches the stage in which it can produce secondary raw materials. As the project matures, it becomes more complex, and reporting on it requires more detailed, reliable, and accurate information. Thus, the guidelines and guidance provided in this document for reporting projects and their classifications are tailored to their maturity and development phase.

This document is a proposal for reporting the environmental-social-economic viability and technical feasibility of secondary raw materials recovery projects, as well as the potential quantities of secondary material raw materials to be recovered, in accordance with the principles of the UNFC. It provides a structured framework for reporting this information, along with relevant terminology and explanations, and suggests the minimum requirements for the information that should be provided. In particular, it can be useful for reporting the UNFC classification of projects seeking recognition as strategic in the EU, as required by the EU Critical Raw Materials Act (European Parliament, 2024). This proposal was developed under the Horizon Europe FutuRaM project, and therefore has a focus on projects in the EU.

This proposal is a working document drafted for the attention of the UNECE¹ EGRM² as an initial step toward the development of a reporting standard. In its current form, it should not be considered a standard for company reporting, nor a document recognized or accepted by any stock exchange markets. Some specific reporting aspects, such as quality assurance procedures and the requirements for qualified experts involved in reporting or independent review, were beyond the scope of this draft and should be addressed in future work.

¹ United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

² Expert Group on Resource Management

2.1 Application

The guidelines and guidance in this document apply to projects in the secondary raw material recovery sector. They follow the conceptual approach developed in the FutuRaM project, which was tested in twelve site-specific UNFC case studies that classified projects for material recovery from Battery Waste, Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment, End-of-Life Vehicles, Slags and Ashes, Construction and Demolition Waste, and Mining Waste, at various stages of development (Heuss-Aßbichler et al., 2025). It is expected that the guidelines and guidance provided in this document will be generally applicable, also to projects addressing other waste streams.

It should be noted that different waste streams may exhibit specific characteristics that can influence the project classification. For example, mining waste often shows substantial variability in composition and may lack sufficient source documentation, or flow-based recovery projects may rely on future trends in waste generation, both of which can increase uncertainties in the G-axis assessment. Similarly, other waste streams may involve technical, environmental, or regulatory features that affect the evaluation of the E- and F-axes. Therefore, project reporting should acknowledge waste-stream-specific particularities and ensure that these are appropriately reflected in the UNFC classification.

2.2 Principles of reporting

The classification report for a project should present all the information necessary to judge and reproduce the classification results. In order to do so, it should consider the following underlying reporting principles, adapted from the Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards (CRIRSCO, 2019):

- **Transparency** requires that the reader of a report be provided with sufficient information presented in a clear and unambiguous manner so as to be understandable and not misleading.
- **Materiality** requires that a report contains all relevant information that project stakeholders, including investors and their professional advisers, authorities, the public, and NGOs reasonably require and would reasonably expect to find in a Public Report for the purpose of making a reasoned and balanced judgement about a project.
- **Consistency** requires that all projects, whether collection, pre-treatment, or treatment of secondary raw materials along a specific value chain, be assessed and classified using a unified, standardized approach. Even if individual projects are not directly comparable on a one-to-one basis, applying a consistent methodology ensures that the information obtained and the resulting classifications are coherent and comparable.

2.3 Type of report

This document aims to propose guidelines and guidance for developing public reports on the classification of secondary raw material recovery projects. In this context, a public report is one that communicates necessary data and information related to a project and its classification to direct and indirect stakeholders, such as investors, authorities, NGOs, and the public.

According to the Guidance for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) for Mineral and Anthropogenic Resources in Europe (UNECE, 2022b), a report on the classification of a project should explain the reasons for the categorization and classification of a

project. Therefore, all information that provides a clear overview of the project and its classification should be provided in the report, including the relevant controlling factors, their ratings, and the corresponding explanation for the ratings, as well as the controlling factors excluded from the classification, together with a justification explaining the reason for their exclusion.

On the other hand, the UNFC 2019 (UNECE, 2020b) states that "*Unless mandated or restricted by a government or other regulatory body, the disclosure of product quantities under UNFC is entirely at the discretion of the reporter*". Hence, if a piece of information that underpins the project categorisation and classification, such as the product quantity, is considered confidential by the project owner, it can be excluded from the public report and provided only in reports developed for specific stakeholders (e.g., investors and authorities). However, if specific information used for the categorisation and classification cannot be included in a public report due to confidentiality and is communicated only to specific stakeholders, the public report should clearly state that such information exists, but cannot be disclosed publicly.

3 Background

This proposal was developed based on the outcomes of the FutuRaM project Task 1.1 (Develop, harmonise and integrate concepts, methods, models, and procedures) (Boga et al., 2025; Kippert et al., 2025), Work Package 5 (Secondary raw materials availability assessment in line with the UNFC) (Heuss-Aßbichler et al., 2025), and meetings held with the partners involved in this deliverable (D1.3).

Information on project inputs and outputs is a core aspect of project reporting. To ensure harmonised collection of this information, a model for the collection of composition data was developed in the FutuRaM project under Task 1.1 (Kippert et al., 2025), which provides standard templates and code lists for waste streams to ensure consistent collection of data, and development of a database across the product, component, material, and element levels. It was suggested to collect the project inputs and outputs information based on this model.

Procedures developed in the FutuRaM project to apply the UNFC for the classification of secondary raw material recovery projects (Heuss-Aßbichler et al., 2025) specify the information required for project classification, provide explanations of relevant terms, and offer guidance on the factors to be considered. It is worth noting that these procedures, as well as the information required to be collected and included in a report, were based on the numerous stakeholder consultations conducted in Work Package 5. These considerations were taken into account in the development of this deliverable.

In addition, a discussion paper entitled "UNFC G-axis use for recycling projects" (Kral et al., 2026) was developed to provide guidance on how to address the degree of confidence associated with product quantity estimates. These outcomes of the FutuRaM project were used to develop the guidelines and guidance presented in this document for reporting the viability of secondary raw materials recovery projects and the associated product quantities.

4 Proposal for the structure and content of the reporting standard

This chapter presents the proposed content and structure of the reporting standard. It includes explanatory descriptions of terminology related to reporting, as well as the requirements regarding the information to be included in reports on the viability of secondary raw materials recovery projects, their quantities, and the associated uncertainties in accordance with the UNFC.

4.1 Reporting terminology

The terms and concepts defined in this section will be used later in the guidelines and guidance for reporting of projects classified under the UNFC. This document uses the same definitions as UNFC 2019 (UNECE, 2020b) and its specifications. For terms not defined therein, definitions or explanations are provided here as needed.

4.1.1 Project

According to the UNECE UNFC 2019 document (UNECE, 2020b):

“A Project is a defined development or operation which provides the basis for environmental, social, economic, and technical evaluation and decision-making.”

4.1.2 Project profile (Basic project information)

The project profile includes basic information that provides a general overview of the project. It is suggested to include the following entries in the report, irrespective of the project development phase.

- Project title
- Waste stream information
- Project development phase
- Products and by-products
- Project lifetime
- Project location, including the spatial coordinates
- Contact person
- UNFC categories and class
- Classification date (Effective date)

4.1.2.1 Project title

The project title provides a brief, clear description of the project that offers an immediate understanding of the project’s purpose and focus within a concise format.

The project title should include:

- Target product(s) to be recovered
- Source waste stream
- Processing method or technology used

4.1.2.2 Waste stream information (as the source of secondary raw material)

The waste stream information, as the source of secondary raw material, should be specified in the project profile (e.g., the FutuRaM waste streams, which were mining waste, battery waste, waste electrical and electronic equipment, construction and demolition waste, wind turbines, slags and ashes, end-of-life vehicles, etc). In UNFC terminology, sources are the origin from which products can be derived (UNECE, 2022).

4.1.2.3 Project development phase

Three development phases of a project are distinguished in this proposal, i.e., screening, pre-feasibility, and feasibility, before implementation (Figure 1). The depth and breadth of data and other information required for reporting increase as a project becomes more mature. The classification results for each development phase may lead to a decision to proceed with the project or to pause it until an obstacle is resolved, after which project development can resume. Figure 1 sets out the framework for classifying projects for the recovery of secondary raw materials from waste streams, in the different stages of project development, from screening to implementation.

Figure 1. Phases of project development and UNFC classes

4.1.2.3.1 Screening phase

The screening phase is the first formal phase of project development, in which the potential of a project idea is evaluated. According to the UNECE Anthropogenic Working Group of the Expert Group on Resource Management (UNECE, 2025):

"In this first stage of the project lifecycle (screening) the presence of anthropogenic sources may be hypothesized but is not yet known or poorly defined at this stage. The entity doing screening may apply techniques such as estimates on feedstock supply in terms of quantity and composition."

Screening relies on limited and uncertain data, allowing only a preliminary assessment of whether a project is worth initiating. Similar to the exploration phase in the mining sector, the focus is on identifying both obstacles and drivers that could influence the project's success. In this phase, the assessment is usually qualitative. Cautionary notes should be provided by the evaluator regarding the uncertainties associated with the data and information. A preliminary analysis using basic information should nevertheless broadly address all the UNFC criteria, including technical, economic, environmental, social, and legal aspects, and also the degree of confidence in the estimated quantity of available materials. The technology readiness level (TRL) (European Commission, 2024) at this phase is typically low, e.g., TRL 1 (basic principles observed) or TRL 2 (technology concept formulated), but screening phase assessment remains appropriate for higher TRLs if other aspects of the project have not been fully established, or information is missing.

4.1.2.3.2 Pre-feasibility phase

According to the UNECE Anthropogenic Working Group of the Expert Group on Resource Management (UNECE, 2025):

"Pre-feasibility study is a more detailed and informative study that contains information such as feedstock composition, demonstrators and advanced process designs."

The pre-feasibility phase builds on the screening phase by conducting more detailed investigations to justify the project's potential for further development. At this stage, the technology is typically at TRL 3 (experimental proof of concept), TRL 4 (technology validated in a lab), or TRL 5 (technology validated in an industrially relevant environment). Even at a higher TRL, the pre-feasibility phase should be considered if other aspects of the project have not yet been fully established or if information is missing. The analysis goes into more detail regarding technical feasibility, economic viability, infrastructure availability, and environmental and social impacts, using a set of controlling factors to assess each UNFC criterion. The UNFC classification of a project in the pre-feasibility phase aims to identify the factors that promote or hinder a project transparently and clearly.

4.1.2.3.3 Feasibility phase

The feasibility phase focuses on the requirements for project implementation, including technical feasibility, economic viability, infrastructure availability, and environmental and social impacts, using a set of controlling factors to assess each UNFC criterion. According to the UNECE Anthropogenic Working Group of the Expert Group on Resource Management (UNECE, 2025):

"Definitive or Bankable Feasibility Studies are advanced stage works based on finalized process designs for the Project."

At this phase, technology is typically at TRL 6 to 9, i.e., ranging from demonstrated to fully operational for its intended purpose. The UNFC classification of a project in the feasibility phase should transparently and clearly highlight the enablers and barriers of a project.

4.1.2.4 Product and by-product

The term “Product³” is defined as follows in the Guidance for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC) for Mineral and Anthropogenic Resources in Europe (UNECE, 2022b):

“The quantity that will cross the reference points of a project and that will be delivered from or consumed by the project.”

Furthermore:

“The Product quantities are defined in quality and quantity by Products, for example, mined or produced ores, ore concentrates or by-products that will cross the Project reference points.”

UNFC 2019 and related guidance documents do not contain a formal, standalone definition of “by-product” in the glossary of UNFC itself. Therefore, the following definition is suggested, which was adapted from the EU Waste Framework Directive (European Parliament, 2008):

“A by-product is a substance or object generated unintentionally as an integral part of a production or recovery process, whose primary purpose is not the production of that substance or object, and which is not considered waste, provided that its further use is certain, it can be used directly without further processing beyond normal industrial practice, and its intended use is lawful.”

4.1.2.5 Project lifetime

According to the UNECE Specifications for the application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources to Anthropogenic Resources (UNECE, 2018a):

“The estimated quantities for a Project shall be limited to quantities that will be produced during the Project Lifetime, which is defined as the economic limit, design life, or contract period for the Project, as defined below. The Project Lifetime can sometimes be limited by the availability of the source material or by the extent of entitlement or social licences. Because of its importance in estimating material quantities, the Project Lifetime and its basis shall be disclosed in association with any reported quantities.”

4.1.2.6 Project location

If the location of the project implementation is already decided, its exact location should be stated in the report by providing the following information:

- **Country:** The country where the project is located. This specifies the nation that governs the project’s operations and legal requirements.
- **Municipality:** The municipality in which the project site is or will be located. This provides a more granular description of the project’s location. It helps define the project’s position within a specific region or community, which is important for logistics and regional planning. In some countries, regulations and permit requirements differ between municipalities. Therefore, information about the municipality can provide an overview of the regulations that must be followed to implement the project.
- **Spatial Coordinates:** The spatial coordinates of the project site. This includes the latitude and longitude coordinates, which can be expressed using different coordinate reference systems,

³ The UNFC definition of “product” differs from the legal definition of the term in European product, waste, and chemical regulations.

such as ETRS89 or WGS 84, or in projected systems such as UTM. This information ensures accurate mapping and location identification.

Contrary to most primary resource recovery projects, some secondary raw material recovery projects may use mobile facilities. This can be stated here, along with any geographical limitations.

4.1.2.7 Contact person

Contact information must be provided for the person best able to answer questions about the project and its classification, if needed. This includes their name, affiliation, and email address to ensure proper communication and access to further details about the project.

4.1.2.8 UNFC Categories and Class

According to UNFC 2019 (UNECE, 2020b), the UNFC categories are defined as:

"Primary basis for classification using each of the three fundamental Criteria of environmental-social-economic viability (related Categories being E1, E2, and E3), technical feasibility (related Categories being F1, F2, F3 and F4), and degree of confidence (related Categories being G1, G2, G3 and G4)."

Also, UNFC 2019 (UNECE, 2020b) defines class as:

"Primary level of resource classification resulting from the combination of a Category from each of the three Criteria (axes)."

The UNFC classes indicate the current status of development of a project, reflecting its maturity in terms of environmental-social-economic viability (E), technical feasibility (F), and degree of confidence in the estimate (G). In Table 1, remaining products not developed from identified projects, prospective project, non-viable project, prospective project, and viable project represent UNFC classes and their definitions. Each UNFC class represents and summarizes the current status of a project in terms of viability and maturity.

Table 1. UNFC class explanations and categorisation on the three UNFC axes (UNECE, 2020b)

Explanation	Class	Minimum Categories		
		E	F	G
The project's environmental-social-economic viability and technical feasibility have been confirmed.	Viable project	1	1	1, 2, 3
The project's environmental-social-economic viability and/or technical feasibility has yet to be confirmed	Potentially Viable projects	2	2	1, 2, 3
	Non-Viable Projects	3	2	1, 2, 3
Remaining products not developed from identified projects.		3	4	1, 2, 3
There is insufficient information on the source to assess the project's environmental-social-economic viability and technical feasibility.	Prospective Projects	3	3	4
Remaining products not developed from identified projects.		3	4	4

4.1.2.9 Classification date (Effective date)

The Classification Date, also known as the Effective Date, refers to the date on which the reported estimates and the classification of the project are officially valid. Europe guidance for the application of UNFC for mineral and anthropogenic resources (UNECE, 2022b) defines Effective date as:

"The date for which assessments are valid."

It marks the specific point in time when the product quantities and other key metrics are assessed and recorded, and used in the project classification. It should be noted that the UNFC class results from a snapshot of the information available at a specific time. If this information changes, the project classification and the effective date shall be updated.

4.1.3 Realm of discourse (ROD)

The realm of discourse (ROD) refers to the context in which a project is classified in accordance with UNFC. The ROD dictates the scope of the controlling factors that should be considered in assessing the UNFC criteria related to E- and F-axes. Annex I provides further information on the ROD and its role in UNFC.

4.1.4 Controlling factors

Controlling factors are used to operationalize the assessment of UNFC criteria on the E- and F-axes for project classification (assessment and categorisation of the G-axis is explained in Chapter 3.3). They ensure that results are reproducible and comparable across projects and highlight project enablers and barriers. Derived from the mining concept of "modifying factors" (CRIRSCO, 2019), controlling factors are used to assess the following criteria:

- E axis
 - **Environmental:** This criterion addresses the environmental impacts caused by the project.
 - **Social:** This criterion addresses the impact of the project on humans and society.
 - **Economic:** This criterion addresses the economic costs and benefits of project implementation and development.
 - **Legal:** This criterion addresses all the legal and regulatory requirements that must be met for project implementation and development. This includes all the necessary permits that must be obtained during various phases of project development.
- F axis
 - **Technical feasibility:** This criterion addresses the feasibility of project implementation in terms of technical and technological aspects, such as, but not limited to, technical readiness level (TRL), availability of infrastructure, and commitment to process deployment.

Controlling factors provide essential data that evolve with project maturity. In early project development phases, the evaluation of controlling factors may be associated with some level of uncertainty, and it may not be possible to provide specific evidence and studies to support the result of their evaluation; however, as more information becomes available with further project development, it is expected that sufficient information will be available to enable clearly evidenced evaluation of controlling factors. The evaluated controlling factors for each UNFC criterion, their

ratings, supporting documentation, and explanations regarding their ratings shall be included in the report to facilitate communication of project classification with stakeholders.

In summary, controlling factors are established to:

- 1) Standardize evaluations; they ensure consistency in assessing projects across various domains and stages.
- 2) Facilitate comparisons; they enable benchmarking and comparison with alternative projects by applying a unified framework.
- 3) Promote transparency; they enhance the transparency of project evaluations by providing a clear and structured approach.
- 4) Support decision-making; they provide a basis for classifying projects based on technical, environmental, economic, and social factors.
- 5) Facilitate communication; they facilitate clear communication among stakeholders by providing a standardized framework.

A list of controlling factors is suggested in Annex II for the Basic ROD, which relies on legal compliance for evaluation of the E-axis criteria.

4.2 Presenting the environmental, social, economic, and legal viability (E-axis) and technical feasibility (F-axis) in the report

Categorization of the E- and F-axes shall be clearly presented and explained in the report so that the reader can easily follow the underlying logic of the assessment and independently reproduce its results. In this regard, it is crucial to clarify the realm of discourse and the controlling factors used to evaluate the environmental, social, economic, and legal viability (E-axis), as well as the technical feasibility of the project (F-axis), within this defined realm of discourse.

The E- and F-axes categorization is based on the results of the assessment of the respective controlling factors and follows the “lowest-rating” approach, meaning that the lowest rating among the controlling factors assessed for each axis is assigned as the overall category of the respective E- or F-axis. Therefore, the assessment results and corresponding ratings of all controlling factors shall be documented in the report.

4.3 Presenting material quantities and categorizing the G-axis in the report

The UNFC G-axis defines the degree of confidence of future product quantities associated with the project, with these quantities being determined at the reference point. Reference point is defined as follows in UNFC 2019 (UNECE, 2020b):

"The Reference Point is a defined location within a development at which the reported estimate or measurement is made. The Reference Point may be the sales, transfer or use point from the development or it may be an intermediate stage, in which case the reported quantities account for losses prior to but not subsequent to the delivery point. The Reference Point shall be disclosed in conjunction with the classification. Where the Reference Point is not the point of sale to third parties (or where custody is transferred to the entity's other operations), and such quantities are classified as E1, the information necessary to derive estimated sales shall also be provided."

The reference point(s) shall be defined and described for the project clearly. The UNFC accepts two alternative approaches for defining the degree of confidence, based on the "Confidence in Estimate" or the "Position in Uncertainty Range". The definitions and supporting explanations are given in the report of the UNFC G-Axis Task Force of the UNECE Expert Group for Resource Management (UNECE, 2024b). A guidance document on how to use the UNFC G axis is currently under development (UNECE, 2026) and expected to be published at the 17th Session of the UNECE Expert Group of Resource Management (27 April – 01 May 2026, Palais des Nations, Geneva).

4.3.1 Minimum content of a report on product quantities and the associated uncertainties

Reporting product quantities and associated uncertainties for a project in the context of UNFC requires specific considerations and the provision of relevant data, information, and explanations, as outlined below.

4.3.1.1 Considerations common to reporting on the screening, pre-feasibility, and feasibility phases

The minimum required content for reporting product quantities and G-axis categorization for projects in the screening, pre-feasibility, and feasibility phases is as follows:

- The G-axis used in the project should be indicated, specifying whether the "Confidence in Estimate" or "Position in Uncertainty Range" (UNECE, 2024b) approach was applied. If "Position in Uncertainty Range" is used, it should be clarified whether a Deterministic Scenario Approach or a Probabilistic Approach was applied.
- A justification should be provided for the choice of approach. The selection should take into account common practice, end-user needs, and the availability of data and applicable methodologies (UNECE, 2026).
- The specific meaning of the G-axis categories should be reported, in alignment with the generic explanations provided in the Guidance on the use of the UNFC G-axis. (UNECE, 2026):
 - If "Confidence in Estimate" has been used, then G1, G2, or G3, respectively, indicate a high, moderate, or low degree of confidence in the estimate of the quantity of future production. Quantities that are estimated primarily on indirect evidence are associated with potential sources of prospective projects and allocated to G4.
 - If "Position in Uncertainty Range" has been used, then G1, G1+G2, or G1+G2+G3 means, respectively, that the estimated quantity is the low, best, or high deterministic scenario, or the P90, P50, or P10 probabilistic estimate. G2 and G3 are categories of incremental quantities, such that G1+G2 and G1+G2+G3 are, respectively, the best and high deterministic scenarios, or the P50 and P10 probabilistic estimates. The G1 to G3 categories are associated with known sources of identified projects, whereas estimates are primarily based on direct evidence. Quantities that are estimated

primarily on indirect evidence are associated with potential sources of prospective projects and allocated to G4.

4.3.1.2 Specific considerations for screening phase

In the screening phase, the total quantities of "products at the source"⁴ are estimated (e.g., lithium in batteries that enter the treatment facility). There may be multiple products at the source, and each product shall be categorized separately. Note that different products may have different G-axis categories.

4.3.1.3 Specific considerations for reporting on the pre-feasibility and feasibility phases

In the pre-feasibility and feasibility phases, the total quantities are divided into a) sold or used quantities, b) unused or consumed in operation quantities, and c) remaining quantities not developed from prospective and identified projects. Quantities shall be separately categorized and reported by considering the following aspects:

- A project might produce different types of products. For example, a treatment facility for end-of-life-vehicles (ELV) produces ferrous, non-ferrous, plastic and mixed waste fractions. Each product type should be categorized separately. Note that different products might have different G-axis categories.
- Quantities of future production can be a) sold or used⁵ or b) unused or consumed in operations⁶. The differences between the total quantities at the source and the sum of sold, used, unused and consumed quantities are labelled as remaining quantities not developed from identified or prospective projects⁷. These three types of quantities shall be separately reported.
- Quantities of past production have been either a) sold or used, or b) unused or consumed in operations. Past production quantities are not categorized on the G axis.
- Quality specifications of the future products according to off-taker needs and recognized industrial standards (e.g. material composition, chemical and physical properties).

4.3.2 Additional reporting considerations

In addition to the points mentioned above, the following should also be taken into account regarding the material quantities reported for a project:

- Remaining quantities not developed from prospective or identified projects may be of relevance for material stocks (e.g., landfills, heaps, extractive waste storage facilities, intermediate storage facilities) but not for material flows (e.g., waste flows entering a treatment facility).
- Double accounting of quantities should be avoided.

⁴ Products at source implies that materials that are expected to be recovered and produced through the project.

⁵ Products that are sold or used are categorized on the EFG axes.

⁶ Products that are unused or consumed in operations are categorized separately on the E axis as E3.1. The E3.1 is defined as "Estimate of product that is forecast to be developed, but which will be unused or consumed in operations".

⁷ Remaining quantities are categorized separately as E3F4. The estimated quantities are categorized on the G axis (as G4 for prospective projects and G1, G2 or G3 for identified projects).

- The UNFC definition of “product” differs from the legal definition of the term in European product, waste, and chemical regulations.

4.4 Reporting of projects in the screening phase in line with UNFC

4.4.1 Overview

A report for a project at the screening phase, assessed according to the UNFC, should include the following headings:

1. Project profile
2. Degree of confidence in materials quantities at source (G-axis)
3. Evaluation of precondition background information
4. Scope of the project
5. Preliminary technical considerations (F-axis)
6. Preliminary economic assessment (E-axis)
7. Preliminary environmental and social impact assessment (E-axis)
8. Legal considerations (E-axis)
9. Stakeholders' information
10. UNFC categorization and classification

4.4.2 Project profile

A project report, irrespective of its development phase, should always start with the project profile (4.1.2). It provides a quick and general overview of the key characteristics of the project.

4.4.3 Degree of confidence in product quantities at source (G-axis)

The reference point lies at the anthropogenic source in the screening phase, and the total quantities of “products at the source⁸” are estimated (4.3.1.2). There may be more than one product in the source. All products and their quantities should be reported and categorised on the G-axis. For instance, if the project idea is to recover materials from e-waste (as the source of materials), the materials in the e-waste should be reported. An overview of the supporting studies and documents available must be provided to justify the G-axis categorization for the products at source.

4.4.4 Evaluation of precondition background information

The main goal of the screening phase evaluation is to decide whether a project idea at a very early stage of development should be pursued (4.1.2.3.1). In this regard, it is suggested to address the following questions in the report, amongst others.

- Is recycling and treatment of the intended waste mandated by law?
- Does the lack of recycling of the waste cause environmental risks?
- Does the lack of recycling of the waste cause social risks (including human health issues)?

⁸ Products at source implies that materials that are expected to be recovered and produced through the project. This is the terminology used in the UNFC documents, including the guidance document on the G-axis.

- Does the waste contain a high concentration of economically valuable materials, e.g., at concentrations comparable or exceeding those in commercially viable primary sources?
- Does the waste treatment bring economic benefits by reducing the costs caused by waste?
- What is the intended ROD for the classification?

The answers to these questions should be clear, comprehensive, and convincing to the reader, with provision of appropriate evidence.

4.4.5 Scope of the project

This section includes images or diagrams to visually represent the project's boundaries and scope. In general, these visuals should be clear, concise, and easy to understand. If possible, they should outline the following information:

- The process flow diagram for the project, including all the processes needed for recovery of the product (e.g., collection, pre-processing, resource recovery)
- Inflow(s) and expected outflows (e.g., products and by-products).
- Reference point (4.3)

4.4.6 Preliminary technical considerations (F-axis)

One of the decisive considerations in the viability of a project is its technical feasibility. Hence, the next point that should be provided in the report for a project classified by UNFC is a description of the preliminary technical considerations. In this regard, the following aspects should be provided in the report.

4.4.6.1 The overall goal of the project

The description of the overall goal of the project clearly defines the purpose and intended outcomes for products. What does the project aim to achieve and how does it contribute to meeting existing needs and objectives?

4.4.6.2 Preliminary technical feasibility assessment

At the early stage of project development, it is important to have a general overview of the technical feasibility of the project and the technology that is supposed to be used to meet the expected outcomes or produce the products. Therefore, it is useful to answer the following questions:

- Has there been any investigation into the technical feasibility of the project?
- Have similar technologies been used in previously implemented projects?
- Is there a technology available to fulfil the expected project outcomes?
- What is the technology readiness level of the intended technology?
- Are the required infrastructures available for project implementation and future operation?

Answering the questions above can support an initial evaluation of the technical feasibility of the project.

4.4.6.3 Potential advantages of intended technology

If the intended technology has already been specified, its potential advantages compared with similar technologies should be considered and included in the report.

4.4.6.4 Preliminary input-output information

Providing an overview of the existing information on the project's input(s) and output(s), including the project's products, by-products, and waste, provides a clear understanding of how the project functions. If available, the supporting studies and documents available, must be provided. In the early stages of project development, the main focus on the inputs (4.3.1.2), and if output quantities are not yet available, it is sufficient to identify the expected outputs without providing quantities.

To enable information comparability and reuse, data about inputs and outputs should be collected consistently across projects using standardised names and codes. This approach enables the development of a harmonised database that brings together relevant material information from all projects. The code lists developed within FutuRaM (Kippert et al., 2025) provide a solid starting point and can be further extended as needed.

4.4.7 Preliminary economic assessment (E-axis)

A summary of the studies and assumptions related to the financial costs and benefits of the project, including the avoided costs because of the project, should be provided in this section.

4.4.8 Preliminary environmental and social impact assessment (E-axis)

The environmental and social benefits that the project brings should be included here, in general terms. If there is any initial study on the environmental and social impact assessment of the project or any other estimation in this regard, its outcome should be included in the report.

4.4.9 Legal considerations (E-axis)

In this section, the legal requirements for implementing the project should be explained, including any required permits. If possible, a list of all required permits should be provided in this section, along with the likelihood of obtaining them. Any obstacles to obtaining the relevant permits should be explained here. Also, if there is evidence of prior success in securing the required permits, this may be used to support the assessment of future permitting feasibility, provided that the earlier permits relate to a similar project and were obtained within the same jurisdiction.

4.4.10 Stakeholder information

In this section, the information on stakeholders, including key entities directly or indirectly involved in, or impacted by the project should be identified and presented, including their roles and contributions.

4.4.11 Categorization and classification

The categories on the E-, F-, and G-axes resulting from assessment of the information, explanations, documents, and evidence about the project provided in the previous sections, and leading to an overall classification of the project, should be reported here. The E- and F-axes categories should be selected based on the conformity of the project's environmental, social, economic, and legal viability and its technical feasibility with the supporting explanations provided for the E- and F-axes categories in UNFC 2019 (UNECE, 2020b).

If the Confidence in Estimate approach is used to assess the project on the G-axis, the lowest G category among the target materials shall be assigned, noting that in the screening phase, this usually relates to the quantity of materials at the source, not to the quantity of materials that will be produced

as project outputs. In case of using the Position in Uncertainty Range approach, the full estimated range (G1, G1+G2, or G1+G2+G3) assigned to the products shall be reported for the project G-axis (4.3).

4.5 Reporting of projects in the pre-feasibility and feasibility development phases

4.5.1 Overview

A report of a project classified under UNFC at the pre-feasibility and feasibility study phases should include the following headings:

1. Project profile
2. Definition of the project and the context of evaluation
3. Degree of confidence in quantities of outputs (G-axis)
4. Evaluation of controlling factors (E- and F-axes)
5. Categorization and classification

4.5.2 Project profile

The first section of the report is the project profile to provide a quick overview of the project. The information should be presented in accordance with Section 4.1.2.

4.5.3 Definition of the project and the context of evaluation

This section focuses on defining the project's scope, goals, and context for the evaluation. It establishes the foundation for the project's classification by providing detailed information as follows and is crucial for ensuring that all relevant aspects of the project are considered before moving on to the next phases of evaluation and classification.

4.5.3.1 Background information

It covers the current status of the project, including the motivations and reasons behind initiating the project. It provides context for why the project is necessary, the challenges it aims to address, and its potential impact on the target waste stream or resource recovery processes.

4.5.3.2 Goal(s) and target(s)

The overall goal of the project is defined here. It reflects the broad aim or purpose of the project, which typically relates to material recovery, recycling, or resource conservation, aligning with sustainability and circular economy principles.

Also, specific objectives or targets of the project should be outlined here. They may include targets related to waste reduction, resource recovery, or environmental and social impacts.

4.5.3.3 Scope of the project

This section outlines the project and includes a flowchart to visually represent the project's boundaries and scope. It should be clear, concise, and easy to understand, demonstrating the following information:

- The source inputs (e.g., waste type or stream)
- The project's processes (e.g., collection, pre-processing, resource recovery)

- The expected outputs (e.g., products, by-products, and waste)
- Reference point

An example is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. An example of the project flowchart

4.5.3.4 Reference point

The Reference Point is a defined location within the development where all measurements, estimates, or classifications will be made. This could be a specific area within the project site where data is gathered for reporting and classification purposes. The information provided in this section, together with the project flowchart, gives a clear illustration of the project.

4.5.3.5 Types of processes

In this section, the type of processes involved in the project, such as collection, material preparation and pre-processing (e.g., dismantling, sorting, crushing, separation, etc.), and materials recovery processes (e.g., mechanical, chemical, and biological) should be introduced and explained in accordance with the project flowchart.

4.5.3.6 Input-output information

This section presents the project's inputs and outputs, specifying quantities, units (e.g., kg/month, tonnes/year), and composition. The level of detail, depending on data confidentiality, may vary from listing input(s) and output(s) for each process (including the materials and energy used) to only the main input(s) and output(s) of the project, including products, by-products, and waste.

Project-specific inputs and outputs information offer insight into the materials, components, and elements relevant to each recovery project. For consistency and comparability across projects, this information should continue to be collected using standardised names and codes. Applying this standardised approach supports the development of a harmonised database that consolidates material information from all projects. The FutuRaM codelists (Kippert et al., 2025) provide a solid starting point and can be extended as needed to capture additional project-specific details.

4.5.3.7 Project jurisdiction and relevant regulations

The jurisdiction in which the project is planned to be implemented, together with the applicable regulations, should be introduced in this section. This determines the governing legal framework and the permits required for project implementation.

4.5.3.8 Realm of discourse (ROD)

The realm of discourse (ROD) specifies the considerations for the selection of controlling factors for UNFC criteria assessment and project classification. Different RODs are introduced and explained in Annex I. In this section, the ROD should be specified as follows:

- **Basic ROD** – If only the legal compliance of the project is considered.
- **CE-ROD (Circular Economy ROD)** – If, in addition to the necessary legal requirements, circular economy principles are considered.
- **UN-SDG-ROD (United Nations Sustainable Development Goals ROD)** – If, in addition to legal requirements and circular economy principles, broader considerations mentioned in the Sustainable Development Goals are considered.

Explaining the selected ROD in the report helps the reader to know what considerations were considered in determining the controlling factors. Please refer to Annex I for further information on RODs.

4.5.4 Degree of confidence in quantities of outputs (products, by-products, and materials in waste)

At the pre-feasibility and feasibility stage, the reference point should be located at the output side of the project, which is typically the point of sale. Consequently, all losses from the source along the processing chain up to the reference points need to be considered. A project may have multiple products and by-products. Their quantities shall be categorised and reported separately in accordance with the considerations set out in Section 4.3. To track the materials that end up in waste, it is recommended to also report the quantity of waste and the concentration of materials, together with their G category. This is particularly helpful for evaluating the circularity of the project.

4.5.5 Evaluation of controlling factors

The controlling factors for the UNFC criteria related to the E- and F-axes should be determined in line with the selected ROD. To evaluate these controlling factors, a specific indicator and a metric should be defined for each one, followed by a rating. Each rating should then be assigned a category corresponding to the relevant UNFC axis. It is necessary to provide a clear explanation, supported by relevant documents and studies, to justify each rating. The selected controlling factors, their evaluation, and the associated explanations and supporting documentation must be included in the report to ensure transparency and reproducibility of the results.

Two examples are provided in Table 2 related to the E- and F-axes for further clarification.

Table 2. Examples of the controlling factors and their rating

UNFC axis	Criteria	Controlling factor	Indicator	Metric & rating	Explanation
E	Legal	Environmental permit	Permit status	Acquired (E1)	Due to some environmental issues related to water pollution, the permit was not granted
				pending (E2)	
				Not permitted (E3) ✓	
F	Technical feasibility	Infrastructure availability	Infrastructure availability status	Available (F1) ✓	All the infrastructure required for project implementation is already available, including road to access the site, power supply infrastructure, water supply system, building and facilities, and wastewater and drainage system
				Mostly available (F2)	
				Partly available (F3)	
				Not available (F4)	

4.5.6 Categorization and classification

The final part of the report presents the UNFC class of the project. The selection of the UNFC E- and F-axes categories is based on the lowest-rating approach, meaning that the controlling factor with the lowest rating determines the final category. For example, if the lowest rating among all controlling factors related to the E-axis is E3, the project shall be categorised as E3.

With respect to the G-axis, when applying the Confidence in Estimate approach, the lowest G category assigned to the products that will be sold as the main output of the project shall be assigned as the project's G category. When applying the Position in Uncertainty Range approach, the full estimated range (G1, G1+G2, or G1+G2+G3) assigned to the products shall be reported for the project G-axis, in accordance with Chapter 4.3.

5 Outlook

This chapter outlines the next steps and road map toward the establishment of a reporting standard aligned with UNFC for reporting the viability and quantities of secondary raw materials recovery projects. It addresses both the further technical development of the draft framework and the process for stakeholder consultation and institutional endorsement necessary for its formal recognition.

5.1 Further development of the technical framework

The present document establishes the initial framework of a UNFC-aligned reporting standard for secondary raw materials recovery projects. To ensure robustness, consistency, and institutional applicability, certain technical components require further elaboration and incorporation in the next phases of development.

5.1.1 Quality assurance

Quality assurance is recognized as a crucial aspect of reliable reporting. The current draft provides the foundational structure and guidance on the information and data to be reported, including project classification, while further development is suggested to define standardized procedures for quality assurance. The qualified expert responsible for classifying the project plays a central role in ensuring the reliability of reported information. In this context, the UNECE EGRM has a dedicated "Competency Working Group"⁹, which developed guidance on the need, definition, and responsibilities of a qualified expert for public reporting functions (UNECE, 2022a). The outputs of this group, along with other relevant inputs, should be considered in the next drafts of this reporting standard. Although the UNECE EGRM "Competency Working Group" has developed guidance on the requirements of a qualified expert for resource estimation, classification, and management, which was resource-neutral, there is a need to define the specific requirements for a qualified expert in the context of secondary raw materials recovery projects.

5.1.2 Linking UNFC terminology with EU terminology

UNFC documents are globally applicable without considering specific jurisdictions. An UNFC-based reporting for European stakeholders would profit from linkages between UNFC terminology to European policies and regulations. For instance, the UNFC documents define the term "product", which should be explained in the context of end-of-waste, waste and by-product definitions according to the (European Parliament, 2008). With respect to Europe, it is therefore recommended to use the UNFC terminology in alignment with relevant EU regulatory terminology to support the consistent terminology in the classification of projects related to secondary raw materials.

5.1.3 Considering all development phases of secondary raw material recovery projects for various waste streams

In this proposal, only the screening, pre-feasibility, and feasibility phases were considered among the project development phases, in line with FutuRaM Work Package 5 (Heuss-Aßbichler et al., 2025). Nonetheless, according to the Supplementary Specification for the Application of UNFC to Anthropogenic Resources (UNECE, 2025), the development phases of a project include screening,

⁹ <https://unece.org/competency-working-group>

scoping, pre-feasibility, feasibility, planning, construction, operation, and closure/reclamation. Therefore, it is suggested that future work on the development of the reporting standard should include all project development phases.

It is also worth noting that the standard terminology for project development phases in the context of material recovery from mining waste differs in some cases from that used in other sectors. For example, the exploration phase is recognized as a development phase following screening. Therefore, harmonization of terminology should also be considered in the development of the reporting standard for various waste streams.

5.1.4 Further clarification on project classification versus classification of resources and commodities

The terms “class” and “classification” require clarification. In the mining sector, they are commonly used to refer to material resources, reserves, and commodities expected to be produced through a mining project. However, in recycling projects (e.g., e-waste or battery recycling), UNFC classes represent the viability level of the projects. It is recommended that this distinction be clarified in future UNFC guidance documents.

5.1.5 Specifying ROD concepts in view of circularity and sustainability, and defining corresponding controlling factors

UNFC was originally developed to assess the maturity and viability of projects based on the degree of confidence in the estimation of a project's product quantity, technical feasibility, and conventional economic viability, with environmental, social, and economic viability assessed primarily in terms of legal compliance. However, establishing a level playing field for the comparison of primary and secondary resource recovery projects across different jurisdictions, in support of the achievement of the SDGs, may require a more detailed assessment of resource circularity and the environmental and social aspects of sustainability. Moreover, several UNECE documents on UNFC (UNECE, 2020a, 2022b, 2024a, 2025) also refer to the consideration of these aspects in project classification, which typically goes beyond legal compliance.

To address the challenge of addressing the circularity and sustainability in UNFC classification, the FutuRaM project suggested utilizing the concept of ROD (see Annex I for further explanation). Addressing circularity and sustainability requires the development of specific controlling factors for the CE-ROD and UN-SDG-ROD. The inclusion of these additional aspects should also be clearly reflected in reporting.

5.2 Stakeholder consultation and institutional endorsement

The UNFC aims to standardize resource management and support decision-making. Its end users are, among others, governments that set framework conditions, capital allocators who invest in the raw material sector, the industry that provides the capability, and international bodies that use UNFC for harmonizing information on the future availability of raw materials. Here are two examples for reporting UNFC data:

- Under the Critical Raw Materials Act (CRM Act), the EU uses the UNFC to compile project-specific information in the mining, processing, and recycling sector. This information supports the recognition of strategic projects and allows the monitoring of development projects before market participation. A template for strategic project applications has been developed

by DG GROW (DG GROW, 2024), and the Commission may adopt implementing acts setting out a template for Member State reporting, as provided for in Article 45 of the CRM Act. Overall, the EU is the first regulatory body that makes UNFC mandatory for reporting recycling projects.

- Countries inventory their mineral resources by using the UNFC. For instance, Ukraine uses the UNFC since 1997 to classify subsoil resources (Netskyi, 2025), the British Geological Survey used UNFC to harmonize resource data for the United Kingdom (Bide, 2021), and researchers developed a mineral inventory for Italy (Sabra et al., 2025). Institutions such as the French Geological Survey (BRGM) have already started to inventory recycling projects by using UNFC terms and principles.

Each of the examples uses its own reporting template to satisfy specific end-user needs. As of today, a standardized UNFC reporting template in analogy to the CRIRSCO template or the NI 43-101 does not exist. Against this background, the following actions are proposed:

- Identification of end users and their needs: The development of a reporting standard aligned with UNFC requires a structured consultation process and institutional validation to ensure transparency, credibility, and broad acceptance. As a first draft developed within the FutuRaM project, this document should be considered a starting point for further discussion with relevant stakeholders.
- Developing a reporting template and guidelines for applying the reporting template under different jurisdictions.
- Testing the application of the reporting template and the guidelines by case studies in consultation with end users.

This proposal is a working document drafted for the attention of the UNECE EGRM as an initial step toward the development of a reporting standard. Hence, it is assumed that UNECE EGRM will continue the work and lead the development of the reporting standard. For the next steps, it is suggested that a structured stakeholder consultation process be conducted to gather comments and feedback from relevant actors, including UNECE EGRM sub-groups, ICE-SRM EU¹⁰, EU Geological Surveys (e.g., GTK, SGU, BRGM, etc), national authorities involved in reporting resource projects such as recycling to the European Commission, DG GROW, industry stakeholders, project developers, and academic experts. Such consultation would help to identify practical challenges, clarify ambiguities, and ensure that the reporting requirements are applicable across different project types related to secondary raw materials recovery projects and jurisdictions.

¹⁰ International Centre of Excellence on Sustainable Resource Management in Europe

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Annex I: The role of the realm of discourse and controlling factors in UNFC

Controlling factors are crucial for ensuring a transparent UNFC classification procedure and for making the results reproducible. Identifying and selecting the controlling factors related to each UNFC criterion is of high importance, and this depends on the requirements and aspects that are considered during project implementation. To this end, it is necessary to specify the scope of the UNFC criteria. Otherwise, the scope of selection of controlling factors will be ambiguous. Some may consider only the controlling factors that are related to legally mandatory requirements for project implementation, whereas others may also include controlling factors addressing sustainability aspects not covered by laws or regulations.

Realm of discourse (ROD)

To specify the scope of UNFC criteria for the selection of controlling factors, the concept of "Realm of discourse (ROD)" is introduced to help clarify the context and conditions under which a project is classified, which aspects are considered in classifying a project, and how the controlling factors are specified. Thus, describing the ROD is of high importance in reporting. This concept was proposed for use in the UNFC by a UNECE Expert Group on Resource Management sub-group, the "Social and Environmental Considerations Task Force". (UNECE, 2018b, 2020a).

The introduction of the ROD, in conjunction with the associated controlling factors, facilitates the incorporation of principles related to circular resource use and sustainability, reflecting best practices in the management of secondary raw materials. Three modules are suggested for ROD as follows (Figure 3):

- **Basic-ROD:** Covers essential controlling factors required for the permitting of the project and mandated by law.
- **CE-ROD (Circular Economy):** In addition to controlling factors from Basic ROD, it includes the controlling factors that are relevant for the material recovery efficiency in line with the circular economy principles.
- **UN-SDG-ROD (Sustainability Development Goals):** In addition to controlling factors from Basic and CE-ROD, it considers controlling factors related to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to ensure the long-term sustainability of projects based on the UN recommendations.

Figure 3. Three modules of the ROD: the mandatory basic-ROD with the controlling factors to achieve approval for a project (the core of the ROD), with the optional CE-ROD (inner-sphere) addressing circular economy requirements. UN-SDG-ROD addressing sustainability issues (outer sphere).

Basic ROD: Legal considerations

Getting the permits and meeting the requirements stipulated in law is the minimum consideration that should be taken into account for assessing the viability of a project. The basic ROD module is focused on legislation and legal considerations related to project implementation. Hence, it only includes essential controlling factors required for the permitting of the project regarding the UNFC criteria. For instance, concerning the environmental criteria, only the aspects that are considered and mentioned in the regulations, such as EIA, are taken into account, and the controlling factors are identified accordingly. Therefore, if there is a specific environmental requirement that goes beyond and is not mentioned in the regulation, it is not included in the basic ROD. The Basic-ROD forms the core and is mandatory, meaning that the controlling factors related to this module will always be considered in classifying a project by UNFC. A comprehensive list of controlling factors was developed and suggested for the Basic-ROD with regard to regulations and directives in the EU in the EU Horizon Europe FutuRaM project, which is provided in Annex II.

CE-ROD: Circular economy considerations

CE-ROD goes beyond the basic ROD and includes additional aspects and controlling factors relevant for the material recovery and efficiency in line with the circular economy principles. The additional controlling factors in CE-ROD, compared to basic ROD, evaluate the project performance in terms of circularity, such as, but not limited to, energy reuse, water reuse, waste recycling, integration in a circular value chain, etc.

UN-SDG-ROD: Sustainability considerations

UN-SDG-ROD is the most comprehensive module, which, in addition to controlling factors related to basic and CE-ROD, includes controlling factors related to requirements mentioned in the UN SDGs.

Annex II: List of Controlling Factors Suggested for UNFC E- and F-axes Criteria for the Basic ROD

Controlling factors	Criteria	ROD	Relevant development phase	Description
Technology readiness level	Technical feasibility	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	What is the technology readiness level?
Infrastructure and logistics	Technical feasibility	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are you able to develop initial site layouts and logistics plans for material handling, storage, and transportation?
Infrastructure status	Technical feasibility	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any local infrastructures available?
Commitment to infrastructure availability	Technical feasibility	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	This factor assesses the project's ability to utilize existing infrastructure or coordinate with external providers to meet its operational needs. It focuses on the readiness of shared infrastructure (e.g., transport networks, utilities, waste management) that can be leveraged for the project. Rather than building new infrastructure, the focus is on accessibility, agreements, and coordination with other stakeholders who control or operate the required infrastructure.
Commitment to process deployment	Technical feasibility	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	This factor evaluates the project's commitment to scaling up and implementing the core process, with a focus on ensuring the operational readiness for the selected process. The emphasis here is on access to proven

				processes and technology, which may involve adapting or adopting existing processes from other projects or providers.
Air quality impact	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will the project release pollutants or any hazardous, toxic or noxious substances into the air (or lead to exceeding Ambient Air Quality standards in Directives 2008/50/EC and 2004/107/EC)?
Water quality impact	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will the project lead to risks of contamination of water from releases of pollutants onto the ground or into surface waters, ground water, coastal waters or the sea?
Soil contamination	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will the project lead to contamination of land?
Noise and vibration impact	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will the project cause noise and vibration?
Light, heat and radiation	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will the project release of light, heat energy or electromagnetic radiation?
Waste generation	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility	Will the project produce solid waste during the construction or operation or decommissioning?
Waste hierarchy compliance	Environmental	Basic	Feasibility	
Use of natural resources	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will the project use natural resources such as land, water, materials or energy, especially any resources which are non-renewable or short in supply?
Transboundary impact	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will there be any potential for transboundary impact?

Environmental sensitivity	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	<p>Is there a risk that protected sites, areas or features will be affected?</p> <p>Are there any other areas on or around the location that are important or sensitive for reasons of their ecology e.g. wetlands, watercourses or other waterbodies, the coastal zone, mountains, forests or woodlands, that could be affected by the Project?</p>
Biodiversity	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any areas on or around the location that are used by protected, important or sensitive species of fauna or flora?
Land use	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will the project involve actions which will cause physical changes in the locality (topography, land use, changes in waterbodies, etc)?
Cumulative impact	Environmental	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any potential for cumulative impacts with other existing or planned activities in the locality?
Investment conditions	Economic	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	The conditions concerning taxes, royalties, & other financial regulations
Investment status	Economic	Basic	Feasibility	
Net present value	Economic	Basic	Feasibility	
Profit margin	Economic	Basic	Feasibility	
Financial risk	Economic	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any potential financial risks such as market volatility and operational costs?

Market demand and prices	Economic	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	What are the demand and price trends for the recovered materials and forecast future market conditions?
Cost-benefit analysis	Economic	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	How are the projected costs with expected revenues and performed sensitivity analysis?
Supply continuity confidence	Economic	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Have waste material sources been assessed for stability, and/or have long-term contracts been secured to ensure a consistent supply?
Permits' status	Legal	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	All permits required to implement the project should be listed as a controlling factor related to the legal criterion for the E-axis, and be rated with regard to their status.
Environmental impact assessment (EIA)	Legal	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	The Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) process evaluates the potential environmental consequences of the project and determines whether mitigation measures are needed. This factor assesses the status of the EIA process, ensuring that environmental regulations and guidelines are followed. It includes screening, scoping, assessment, public consultation, and approval stages as per relevant legislation (e.g., Directive 2011/92/EU on EIA).
Commitment to supply (input) continuity	Legal	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	This factor assesses the availability and reliability of input materials necessary for the project's operation. It considers contractual agreements, supply chain stability, potential disruptions, and legal obligations related to securing raw materials or feedstock.
Human health	Social	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any concerns about actual or perceived risks to human health or welfare?

Socio-economic impact	Social	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will the project result in social changes, for example, in traditional lifestyle and employment?
Risk of accidents/disasters	Social	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Will there be any risk of accidents during construction or operation of the project which could affect human health, safety or the environment?
Public feedback	Social	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	The engagement of the public including stakeholders, local communities, NGOs, and government agencies, to gather input and build support for the project.
Cultural heritage	Social	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any areas or features of historic or cultural importance on or around the location which could be affected by the project?
Landscape	Social	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any areas or features of high landscape or scenic value on or around the location which could be affected by the project?
Population	Social	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any areas on or around the location which are densely populated or built-up, which could be affected by the project?
Impact on sensitive lands	Social	Basic	Pre-feasibility, Feasibility	Are there any areas on or around the location which are occupied by sensitive land uses, e.g. hospitals, schools, places of worship, and community places, which could be affected by the project?